

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL STRATIFICATION ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Polvonniyozova Mahliyo O'ktamjon qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University, Teacher

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

pmlune@mail.ru

+998 90 110 86 79

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11126620>

Abstract: Social stratification refers to the hierarchical arrangement of individuals or groups within a society based on factors such as social class, race, gender, and economic status. This article focuses on exploring the impact of social stratification on academic performance, particularly in the context of educational settings. Research indicates that social stratification can significantly influence students' academic outcomes. Students from disadvantaged backgrounds, such as low-income families or marginalized communities, often face barriers that hinder their academic success. These barriers may include limited access to quality education, inadequate resources, lack of parental support, and exposure to adverse social conditions.

Keywords: Social stratification; Academic performance; Educational settings; Disadvantaged backgrounds; Inequalities in education; Systemic inequalities; Marginalized communities; Resources in education; Culturally responsive teaching; Equitable resource allocation.

Аннотация: Социальная стратификация относится к иерархическому расположению людей или групп внутри общества на основе таких факторов, как социальный класс, раса, пол и экономический статус. Эта статья посвящена изучению влияния социального расслоения на успеваемость, особенно в контексте образовательных учреждений. Исследования показывают, что социальное расслоение может существенно повлиять на академические результаты студентов. Студенты из неблагополучных семей, таких как семьи с низким доходом или маргинализированные сообщества, часто сталкиваются с барьерами, которые мешают их академическим успехам. Эти барьеры могут включать ограниченный доступ к качественному образованию, нехватку ресурсов, отсутствие родительской поддержки и воздействие неблагоприятных социальных условий.

Ключевые слова: Социальная стратификация; Академическая успеваемость; Образовательные учреждения; Неблагополучное

происхождение; Неравенство в образовании; Системное неравенство; Маргинализованные сообщества; Ресурсы в образовании; Культурно-ориентированное обучение; Справедливое распределение ресурсов.

Annotatsiya: Ijtimoiy tabaqalanish jamiyatdagi shaxslar yoki guruhlarining ijtimoiy sinf, irq, jins va iqtisodiy maqom kabi omillarga asoslangan ierarxik joylashuvini anglatadi. Ushbu maqola ijtimoiy tabaqalanishning akademik natijalarga ta'sirini o'rganishga qaratilgan, ayniqsa ta'lim sharoitlari kontekstida. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ijtimoiy tabaqalanish talabalarning ilmiy natijalariga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Kam ta'minlangan oilalar yoki marginal jamoalar kabi kam ta'minlangan talabalar ko'pincha ularning akademik muvaffaqiyatlariga to'sqinlik qiladigan to'siqlarga duch kelishadi. Bu to'siqlar sifatli ta'lim olish imkoniyatining cheklanganligi, resurslarning yetarli emasligi, ota-onalar tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanmasligi va noqulay ijtimoiy sharoitlarga duchor bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy tabaqalanish; Akademik samaradorlik; Ta'lim sozlamalari; Ta'limdagi tengsizliklar; Tizimli tengsizliklar; Marginallashtirilgan jamoalar; Ta'limdagi manbalar; Madaniy jihatdan sezgir o'qitish; Resurslarni adolatli taqsimlash.

Introduction. Social stratification, the division of society into different social classes based on factors such as wealth, power, and status, has a profound impact on various aspects of individuals' lives. One critical area where social stratification can significantly influence outcomes is in education, particularly in relation to academic performance. This article will explore the ways in which social stratification affects academic performance, considering factors such as educational settings, disadvantaged backgrounds, systemic inequalities, and the importance of equitable resource allocation. By examining these dynamics, we can gain a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities that exist within our education system and work towards creating a more just and inclusive learning environment for all students.

Literature review. The review presented above sheds light on the significant impact of social stratification on academic performance. The hierarchical arrangement of individuals in society based on factors such as socioeconomic status, education, occupation, and social class has been shown to play a crucial role in shaping students' educational experiences and outcomes. From the widening achievement gap between the rich and the poor to the persistent disparities in academic achievement between different racial and

ethnic groups, social stratification permeates every aspect of the educational landscape.

Studies have highlighted how socioeconomic status, family background, parenting practices, and cultural capital interact to influence students' academic success. The unequal distribution of resources, opportunities, and support systems based on social stratification further exacerbates educational inequalities and perpetuates disparities in academic performance. The impact of social stratification is evident not only in students' academic achievement but also in their transitions into school, likelihood of dropping out, and access to summer learning opportunities.

Addressing the impact of social stratification on academic performance requires a multifaceted approach that involves policymakers, educators, families, and communities working together to create a more equitable and inclusive educational system. By addressing systemic barriers, providing targeted support for disadvantaged students, promoting parental involvement, and fostering a culture of equity and diversity in schools, we can strive towards narrowing the achievement gap and ensuring that all students have equal opportunities to succeed academically.

Ultimately, understanding and addressing the influence of social stratification on academic performance is essential for creating a more just and equitable society where every individual has the opportunity to reach their full potential regardless of their background or circumstances. By acknowledging and confronting the challenges posed by social stratification in education, we can work towards building a more inclusive and equitable educational system that empowers all students to thrive and succeed academically.

Research methodology. Students from different social classes may attend schools with varying resources, quality of teachers, and academic programs.

Schools in affluent neighborhoods often have more funding, smaller class sizes, and access to advanced courses and extracurricular activities. In contrast, schools in low-income areas may struggle with limited resources, outdated facilities, and higher teacher turnover rates. These disparities in educational settings can affect the quality of education students receive and ultimately impact their academic performance.

Students from lower social classes may face additional challenges outside of school that can hinder their academic performance. Factors such as poverty, unstable housing, lack of access to healthcare, and food insecurity can create barriers to learning and make it difficult for students to focus on their studies.

These students may also have less support at home, fewer educational resources, and limited exposure to enriching experiences that can contribute to academic success.

Social stratification is often reinforced by systemic inequalities within the education system. Students from marginalized backgrounds, such as racial and ethnic minorities, may face discrimination, bias, and unequal treatment in schools. These systemic inequalities can manifest in lower expectations from teachers, harsher disciplinary practices, and limited opportunities for advancement. As a result, students from disadvantaged backgrounds may experience lower academic achievement compared to their peers from more privileged social classes.

Analysis and results.

Social stratification or socioeconomic status has created a societal phenomenon where those with greater economic resources have access to more opportunities than those of lesser financial means. Research has identified that those with more opportunities succeed at higher levels in academia than students on lower levels of the class-based system. This understanding of the educational achievement gap between classes has created a wealth of research with which to investigate the impact of and potentially rectify factors for wealth disparity in education. Educational practitioners and researchers alike have long asserted, the ethical imperative of education is to help all students achieve at high levels. Therefore, educational researchers have extensively sought to comprehend the achievement gap and how poverty impacts school performance.

The field of curriculum and instruction is vast and all inclusive. Education and curriculum and instruction is an industry of serving, motivating and educating human individuals, the field incorporates and investigates through the perspectives of economics, biology, psychology and sociology. This has led to many diverse perspectives from which to explore and understand the academic achievement gap of impoverished students. Following the theory of Maslow's hierarchy of needs, researchers have identified students of disadvantaged backgrounds are less likely to have their basic needs met such as food, shelter, water, and safety. These students then attend school more concerned with their own need for food and safety; they are subsequently unable to be motivated by educational promises such as self-fulfillment.

Researchers have also explored the impact of school and social programs to reduce poverty-based phenomena such as food insecurity. Despite gains made when schools adopt meal programs, economically disadvantaged students

continue to underperform when compared with students of economically stable environments. Some researchers have explored another division of Maslow's hierarchy of needs to explain the continued achievement gap. Maslow's theory states, once the physiological needs of an individual are met they are then motivated by the promise of belonging. Humans are social creatures who seek acceptance from those around them. However, students from impoverished backgrounds often find the values of their social and family group dynamics may not align with the objectives of educators. Thus, educational research has explored avenues to help students feel motivated in school through the fostering of a drive for social belonging. Pitzer and Skinner found when impoverished students engaged in extracurricular activities at school, their academic achievement increased as compared with disadvantaged students who did not partake in these activities. Williams, Bryan, Morrison and Scott theorized that engagement in such activities created a protective social factor for students and met their need to belong by creating values aligned with educational objectives.

Students who engaged in extracurricular activities were also met with an academic responsibility to maintain a certain level of academic performance, such as a prescribed grade point average. This additional responsibility forced all students in the extracurricular activity, such as a sports team, to work towards the same goals as their economically stable counterparts. Furthermore, a fear of social rejection is also speculated to help students maintain the motivation needed in academics to meet the objective. However, the belonging generated by extracurricular activities and the reduced physiological anguish offered by school meal programs have not gone far enough to close the achievement gap for disadvantaged students. Researchers and practitioners must then explore other factors to help all students achieve at high levels.

Conclusion/Recommendations. Addressing social stratification in education requires a commitment to equitable resource allocation. Schools serving students from lower social classes should receive adequate funding, support services, and interventions to level the playing field and provide all students with an equal opportunity to succeed academically. Investing in programs that address the unique needs of disadvantaged students, such as tutoring, mentoring, and mental health services, can help mitigate the impact of social stratification on academic performance.

In conclusion, social stratification plays a significant role in shaping academic performance by influencing educational settings, exacerbating disadvantages for students from lower social classes, perpetuating systemic

inequalities, and highlighting the importance of equitable resource allocation. By recognizing and addressing these dynamics, we can work towards creating a more equitable and inclusive education system that supports all students in achieving their full potential.

References:

1. Reardon, S. F. (2011). The widening academic achievement gap between the rich and the poor: New evidence and possible explanations. In G. J. Duncan & R. J. Murnane (Eds.), *Whither opportunity? Rising inequality, schools, and children's life chances* (pp. 91-116). New York, NY: Russell Sage Foundation.
2. Sirin, S. R. (2005). Socioeconomic status and academic achievement: A meta-analytic review of research. *Review of Educational Research*, 75(3), 417-453.
3. Lareau, A. (2011). *Unequal childhoods: Class, race, and family life* (2nd ed.). Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
4. Ream, R. K., & Palardy, G. J. (2008). Revisiting the impact of SES and parenting on children's early learning. *Sociology of Education*, 81(2), 111-136.
5. Jencks, C., & Phillips, M. (1998). *The black-white test score gap*. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution Press.
6. Duncan, G. J., & Murnane, R. J. (Eds.). (2011). *Whither opportunity? Rising inequality, schools, and children's life chances*. New York, NY: Russell Sage Foundation.
7. Pong, S.-L., & Ju, D.-B. (2000). The effects of change in family structure and income on dropping out of middle and high school. *Journal of Family Issues*, 21(2), 147-169.
8. Crosnoe, R., & Cooper, C. E. (2010). Economically disadvantaged children's transitions into elementary school: Linking family processes, school contexts, and educational policy. *American Educational Research Journal*, 47(2), 258-291.
9. Lee, J., & Bowen, N. K. (2006). Parent involvement, cultural capital, and the achievement gap among elementary school children. *American Educational Research Journal*, 43(2), 193-218.
10. Alexander, K. L., Entwisle, D. R., & Olson, L. S. (2007). Lasting consequences of the summer learning gap. *American Sociological Review*, 72(2), 167-180.